

RADx-UP IMAGE BANK SCOPE OF WORK

02/03/2022

OVERVIEW

1. Project Background and Description

Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics – Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) projects and community partners need to have images, including photographs, that are representative of the diverse populations and communities the projects serve. The representations that can be currently found in print and online do not meet the diverse needs of the RADx-UP projects. Hence, the RADx-UP Image Bank, which will be housed within Box and will be maintained by the Engagement Resource Center (ERC) personnel, has been created to provide a place for members of the RADx-UP community to download, submit, share, and use photographs and images of diverse community members during the COVID-19 pandemic. The RADx-UP Image Bank will contain project and community member submitted photos with accompanying stories that document their experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic.

2. Project Scope

The scope of this image bank is to provide a place for project and community member photographs and story submissions to be housed for all members of the RADx-UP community to use and share. The image bank will allow for both RADx-UP projects and community members to submit photographs and personal COVID-19 stories through the myRADx-UPHome portal, for project submissions, or a Qualtrics link, for community member submissions. The images may then be used by the RADx-UP CDCC and RADx-UP projects for literature, websites, media (print, online, and television), conferences, and publications. The RADx-UP CDCC will contract with community-based photographers in the geographic locations of RADx-UP projects for photographs and stories from those communities. All submissions and entries into the RADx-UP Image Bank will be assessed to ensure the images reflect racial, ethnic, gender, socioeconomic background, and abilities that represent the diversity of RADx-UP projects. The RADx-UP Image Bank will be stored in a secure folder on Box where projects and community partners within the RADx-UP program to request access.

3. High-Level Requirements

- Consent must be obtained from every individual appearing in a photograph.
- Crowd scenes where no single person is the dominant feature is exempt from consenting.
- RADx-UP projects and community members at large can submit photographs with text detailing the photographs' story.
- All photographs and stories will be the property of the RADx-UP CDCC and for use by the CDCC and RADx-UP projects (including Rapid Research Pilot Program and the Community Collaboration Grants).
- Contract with community-based photographers.

4. Deliverables

The RADx-UP Image Bank project began in July 2021. IRB submission will take place in February 2022, followed by identifying and contracting with community-based photographers. Project photograph and story submissions will be submitted via myRADx-UPHome through July 2022. Community members will be able to submit photographs and stories via Qualtrics link. Once the RADx-UP Image Bank project is complete, RADx-UP projects and community

partners will have access to all images, photographs, and COVID-19 stories for the duration of the RADx-UP program, or at a time in the future TBD.

5. Affected Parties

- RADx-UP Engagement Resource Center personnel: Will maintain the RADx-UP Image Bank.
- Box: Will house the RADx-UP Image Bank.
- myRADx-UPHome: Projects can submit photographs for the RADx-UP Image Bank.
- Qualtrics: Community members can submit photographs for the RADx-UP Image Bank.
- Community-based photographers: Individuals contracted through RADx-UP CDCC to take photographs of members of their communities and record the members' COVID-19 stories.
- RADx-UP Projects: Will be able to request access to the RADx-UP Image Bank to utilize images, photographs, and stories for presentations, newsletters, media, COVID-19 messaging, publications, and other activities not yet known.

6. Implementation Plan

The RADx-UP Image Bank will be submitted to the DUHS IRB in February 2022. The RADx-UP CDCC will also contract with photographers from several RADx-UP communities to take photographs of community members for submission to the RADx-UP Image Bank. The photography initiative will be presented to RADx-UP projects through the EITs and at monthly project meetings. Around 10 interested projects will be selected to submit photographs to the RADx-UP Image Bank. The RADx-UP CDCC will submit the RADx-UP Image Bank project to the DUHS IRB and once the project is approved the RADx-UP CDCC will begin contracting with community-based photographers. All community members who are photographed will be informed and consented prior to having their photograph or image taken and they will be able to voluntarily give their story in writing for submission to the RADx-UP Image Bank. Community members, at large, will also be able to submit photographs to the RADx-UP Image Bank. People appearing in photographs submitted by community members will be consented prior to having their photograph submitted to the RADx-UP Image Bank.

7. High-Level Timeline/Schedule

The RADx-UP Image Bank project began in July 2021 and is expected to be complete by July 2022.